

Example Data Management Plan – concise version

Failure of vein grafts and the impact on cardiovascular health after coronary artery bypass surgery

Data Stewardship Wizard (DSW) Example Data Management Plan

Concise version

Organisation
ELIXIR-UK

Created by

Gabriela

Perez Vieira

[id_0000-0001-8860-9571](https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8860-9571)

Based on

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I. Data areas and data types

Prospective, in vivo Positron Emission Tomography (PET) and Computed Tomography (CT) imaging study on saphenous vein graft failure and the wider implications of coronary artery bypass graft surgery. The data will be quantitative, generated from two sources: 1. in vivo PET-CT and CT images, as well as their subsequent analysis, and 2. medical records, electronic health records, and clinical measurements.

II. Standards and metadata

Patient data will be anonymised, recorded in case report forms and transferred to a Microsoft Excel database. We will use Common Data Elements from the NIH Common Data Elements Repository for data collection and the Medical Imaging and Data Resource Center (MIDRC) Commons dictionary for imaging data. Data standards expected to be used <http://ncri-pet.org.uk/index.php>; DICOM (Digital Imaging and Communications in Medicine, <https://www.dicomstandard.org>). Descriptive metadata will be produced at the time of publication/presentation of research outputs. This will include details of the methodology used to obtain and subsequently analyse our data, allowing other researchers to perform related analyses in subsequent studies. Documentation will be developed carefully to ensure it provides sufficient information to understand the content without disclosing details that could be used to re-identify individuals.

III. Relationship to other data available in public repositories

The data generated in this project is not yet publicly available. We plan to collect new data for this proposal.

IV. Secondary use

Due to its strong association with clinical outcomes, graft status may be a useful surrogate outcome in clinical trials of patients undergoing coronary artery bypass grafting. Insights will be developed based on this information, and this will help identify key drivers of development and innovation in this area.

V. Methods for data sharing

Any data that can be shared publicly will be stored in existing public databases. Due to their large size, the datasets may be spread across different repositories, such as Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/>), the UK Data Service, and institutional open repositories. All repositories will provide a digital object identifier (DOI), which can be used by anyone who cites this data in the future.

VI. Proprietary data

Participants in the research studies will be asked for their consent before taking part. The consent forms will clearly state that participants agree to share anonymised data with our research partners. The data will be shared promptly and will be made public through oral and poster presentations, as well as research paper publications.

VII. Timeframes

Data will be made accessible to others promptly. Data will be released at the same time as any published outputs that are underpinned by the data or within one year from the end of the project at the latest.

VIII. Format of the final dataset

Digital data will be recorded in Microsoft Office Word, Excel files and PDFs. Image analysis for all images will be performed using the FusionQuant software (Cedars Sinai Hospital, Los Angeles). Mean and maximum standardised uptake values (SUV) for radiotracer uptake will be measured, and target to background ratios (TBR) will be calculated.